

RF: Central Federal District (Presidential Decree)
 The district comprises the greatest number of regions. Moscow, is the only center for the district. The *Moscow oblast* dominate through their size and political importance (p. 77 [1]). There are/were (!) seven Military Districts (MDs), therein (p. 80 [1])

The seven macro-regions of the Ministry of the Interior (MVD) have been taken as the template for the Administrative Districts. However MVD had several other divisions, with different geographic borders, and these units were not particularly well integrated into the District system (p.81 [1]).

04.06.2001: MVD have been granted the regional offices of that Ministry in 85 regions [1].

DNR (Special statute; Minsk II Agreement, 01.09.2014)

RF: Federal District (not Military one)

According to the Constitution, there are 89 regions [1,5] of five different types: 'proper Russian' oblast and kray (55), federal cities (2); 'ethnic' republics (21), autonomous oblast (1), and autonomous districts (10) [1]. The Constitutional entities of the Russian Federation are determined within Article 65 (1) [2]. Article 65 (1) states that Moscow, St. Petersburg, and Sevastopol' are cities of federal significance [2]. There is not listed the word 'District' among these Constitutional entities of the Russian Federation within the Article 65 (1).

The word 'District' is used to only Article 129 (6) [2].

The Federal District as administrative structural unit of the Russian Federation could be found translated as okrug [4]. The word 'Okrug' is not found within the Article 65. The Federal okrug (district) has been design to weaken the power of regional leaders, not to enhance it [4]. Rather, it reflects existing economic linkages, There are seven okrug (Federal districts).

Article 129 (6): Unless otherwise established by federal law, public prosecutors of cities, districts and public prosecutors equated with them shall be appointed and dismissed by the Prosecutor General of the Russian Federation.

The Republic (state) has its own Constitution and legislation. Krai, Oblast, Federal city, Autonomous oblast, and Autonomous Okrug has its own charter and legislation (p. 10268 [3]). In relations with Federal bodies of state power of subjects of the Russian Federation there is equality and self-determination.

[1] N. Petrov, Seven Faces of Putin's Russia: Federal Districts as the New Level of State-Territorial Composition. Security Dialogue PRIO. SAGE Pubs. 33 (1) (2002) 73-91 ISSN: 0967-0106 [023886].
 [2] Text of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION CONSTITUTION translated by the Constitutional Court for the Opinion (No. 992 / 2020) of the EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR DEMOCRACY THROUGH LAW (VENICE COMMISSION) (Strasbourg, 4 February 2021) [CDL-REF(2021)010]
 [3] D. Tumanov, R. Sakhapov, Subjects of the State within the Russian Federation: Constitutional and Legal Framework. Int. J. Environ. Sci. Edu. 11 (2016) 10265-10277.
 [4] L. Nelson, I. Kuzes, Political and Economic Coordination in Russia's Federal District Reform: A Study of Four Regions. Europe-Asia Studies 55 (2003) 507-520.